

Deliverable 5.3

INNOVATION IMPACT SYNERGIES

Innovation Impact Synergies

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Glossary of terms and acronyms used

ACTRONYM/TERM	DESCRIPTION
ABM	Agent-Based Model
API	Application Programming Interface
BI	Business Intelligence
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CC	Creative Commons
CEMAS	World Sustainable Urban Food Centre of Valencia
CIG	City Interest Group
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
CS	Case Study
CSCP	Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production
DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research & Innovation (European Commission)
DG SANTE	Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety (European Commission)
EC	European Commission
ECESP	European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform
ECFWF	European Consumer Food Waste Forum
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership – Agricultural Productivity & Sustainability
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
ETP	European Technology Platform
EU	European Union
EUFIC	European Food Information Council
F2F	Farm-to-Fork
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FIAB	Spanish Food and Drink Industry Federation
FLW	Food Loss & Waste
GA	Grant Agreement
HoReCa	Hotels, Restaurants and Cafés
HUMAT	Socio-cognitive agent architecture (from H2020 SMARTEES)
ICLEI	Local Governments for Sustainability
ILVO	Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food
INLEIN	Project partner; Task 5.3 lead
IP	Intellectual Property
JRC	Joint Research Centre (European Commission)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LOWINFOOD	H2020 project “LOWINFOOD”
ML	Machine Learning
MOA	Motivation, Opportunity, Ability
MS	Milestone
MS8	Milestone 8 (“Innovation impact synergies”)
NFTP	National Food Technology Platforms
OA	Open Access
REA	European Research Executive Agency

ACTRONYM/TERM	DESCRIPTION
RETASTE	International conference on food waste (RETASTE)
RDI	Research, Development and Innovation
RTD	Research & Innovation (DG RTD shorthand)
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SMARTEES	H2020 project “SMARTEES”
SN	Social Norms
TNW	ToNoWaste (sister project)
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UCPH	University of Copenhagen
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UNIBO	University of Bologna
WP	Work Package
ZeroW	Horizon project “ZeroW”

Executive summary

This deliverable documents how CHORIZO created “innovation impact synergies” through a two-track approach defined in Task 5.3: interfacing project outputs with EC-driven initiatives for open access and reuse, and clustering with relevant and active EU FLW projects to prepare joint federation and syndication of service-oriented assets. Covering activity from M25 to M36, it builds explicitly on WP6 liaison channels and supports tracking of MS8 “Innovation impact synergies.”

Section 1 clarifies the purpose and scope: to evidence, with verifiable artefacts, how CHORIZO’s results have been made findable and reusable beyond the consortium while laying the governance groundwork for post-project federation. **Section 2** sets the rationale and selection logic for clustering, aligning with EU policy frames and describing how partners and channels were prioritised for the greatest leverage and least duplication.

Section 3 reports the EC-facing interface work. CHORIZO positioned its core assets on the EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub through a set of public resources, most notably the Insigner Status Report, the composite indices methodology, and capacity-building items, so that decision-makers and practitioners can locate and reuse the tools and methods. Complementarity with the European Consumer Food Waste Forum and publication of practice abstracts via the CAP network further widened discovery.

Section 4 documents the clustering proper and the federation/syndication pathway. Collaboration with *ToNoWaste* (GA 101059849) and *COMBINE* (GA 101158394) took the form of structured exchanges focused on method and tool alignment, with data exchange and guided feedback to the CHORIZO Insigner tool agreed in principle but not enforced within the reporting period. With *ZeroW* (GA 101036388), clustering culminated in a co-programmed multi-stakeholder final conference in Brussels on 16 September 2025. Beyond EU projects, an exploratory presentation was delivered to *FAO* on 31 July 2025 to explore showcasing and synergies on international platforms. The section also consolidates evidence that CHORIZO’s assets are ready for syndication, i.e. Insigner (the Datahub) functioned as the outward-facing catalogue; the Rapid Appraisal/Visualizer (D3.5) packaged the modelling outcomes into a web-based “what-if” interface built on HUMAT–MOA and the Pantry Manager microsimulation to enable inspection, replication and reuse without code-level integration; and the T4.3 board game that translated social-norms insights into a classroom tool. Capacity-building feedback across actor groups corroborates demand and user-perceived value.

Section 4 also states the variance against the most ambitious federation KPI: in line with end-phase timing and meeting conclusions, no Memoranda of Understanding or Service Level Agreements (SLA) were executed by M36; instead, the project delivers a readiness framework and draft SLA templates to enable post-project federation, and codifies service-agreement principles covering scope, roles and responsibilities, access and use rights, quality, sustainability, feedback, and operational commitments.

Section 5 situates these results in communication and dissemination practice, showing how joint programming, shared sessions and Café Talks with sister and peer projects, alongside the Hub entries, amplified reach while avoiding duplication. Together the sections evidence that CHORIZO’s outputs are openly accessible, actively used and packaged for reuse, and that a pragmatic, “federate-then-syndicate” path is in place for continued collaboration and uptake beyond the project’s end.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 CHORIZO concept and approach

CHORIZO improves understanding of how social norms influence behaviour regarding FLW generation and supports decision-making of food chain actors towards zero food waste. Moreover, CHORIZO translates into evidence the results from previous FLW actions on the role of existing social norms in actors' FLW behaviours and it generates new evidence on social norms & FLW behaviours derived from the project real-life Case Studies (CSs).

CHORIZO drives these research results into innovation products that can accelerate change of FLW-related social norms, by providing guidance, communication & science education packages and capacity building actions. CHORIZO also utilizes advanced modelling techniques to produce solutions that integrate behavioural and economic theories and gender and intersectional analysis to interpret social norm and behavioural data to effectively engineer innovation processes and outputs.

CHORIZO (i) provides information and data on the context and impact of previous FLW prevention/reduction actions; (ii) generates new evidence on the interaction between social norms, behaviour and food waste; (iii) validates the communication & science education packages of the project through the employment of 6 case studies.

CHORIZO consortium comprises of 14 partners, all of whom are involved in the CSs. This structure incentivizes the co-creation of solutions by food chain actors, and research experts, thus, CHORIZO brings significant scientific expertise (ABM, ML / MOA, HUMAT) combined with the real-life needs and experiences of the Case Study members in the consortium.

1.2 Purpose of the Deliverable

This report is prepared in the context of CHORIZO WP5 – Innovation upscaling, which aims to promote the adoption and innovation upscaling of CHORIZO project outcomes. The purpose of this document D5.3 – Innovation Impact Synergies is to ensure that the CHORIZO results are openly available to the wider community of EU FLW interest groups and boost overall impact with the active collaboration and clustering with fellow FLW projects.

Based on Figure 1 below, there is a bilateral connection of this task to T5.2 'Upscaling Strategy for the Services Layer of the CHORIZO 'Insighter' and T5.4 'Sustainability Strategy emphasising the EU's Food Waste Associations'. At the same time, it takes as input the work from T5.1 'IP/Innovation Management' which includes all the innovative outcomes of the project and builds on the liaison activities of WP6. This deliverable also supports tracking of MS8 – Innovation impact synergies introduced in the GA amendment.

Figure 1 Interrelations between the different work components (source: CHORIZO GA, Figure 11)

2 BACKGROUND

2.1 Overview of the project’s results and Outputs

From the beginning of the project and as part of the T5.1 IP/Innovation Management, all partners have been requested to catalogue their outputs/results. As described in detail in the deliverable D5.1 Innovation Management & Exploitation, the Outcomes Registry was created to gather the project outcomes and help understanding the innovation and general impact of each one of them.

In total 13 outcomes were documented in the Outcomes Registry and will be presented below. Nevertheless, a separate file was created in parallel to include also some results which are typical to the project and also facilitate the Communication and dissemination part. Table 1 All CHORIZO outputs Table 1 includes the exhaustive list of the abovementioned results.

Table 1 All CHORIZO outputs

OUTPUT NAME	OUTPUT DESCRIPTION	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER
Research findings CS1	New insights on the role of social norms in FLW behaviours in households, based on CS1 research executed in Belgian and Spanish context.	EV-ILVO
Research findings CS2	New insights on the role of social norms in FLW behaviours in the hospitality sector, based on CS2 research executed in Norwegian hotels.	NORCE
Research findings CS3	New insights on the role of social norms in FLW behaviours in HoReCa sector, based on CS3 research with interactions between retail, restaurants and consumption.	ITC
Research findings CS4	New insights on the role of social norms in FLW behaviours of young people especially in school setting, based on CS4 research executed in Denmark with focus on School lunch-pack.	UCPH
Research findings CS5	New insights on how social norms are influencing the decision-making process in the corporate environment, especially food processors, food retailers and HoReCa companies.	HFBA
Research findings CS6	New insights on how date marking and smart packaging influence FW behaviour among consumers and industry actors conducted in five EU countries.	CNTA
Scientific articles	2 peer reviewed articles describing the evidence-based analysis results.	VLTN, ICLEI, UCPH
Scientific articles	1 peer-reviewed article, presenting the structure of the FLW index and its use in prioritising actions.	VLTN
Scientific articles	6 peer-reviewed articles, presenting the interaction between social norms and FLW behaviour, based on the empirical data generated by the CSs.	various
Scientific articles	1 peer-reviewed article, presenting the Integrated MOA - HUMAT modelling framework, and its deployment in the project.	UNIBO
WP1 outputs	Evidence-based analysis and sector-specific guidance	EV-ILVO

OUTPUT NAME	OUTPUT DESCRIPTION	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER
Rapid appraisal tool	A modelling tool with results from the simulations exercise to be exploited by a different range of stakeholders.	UNIBO
CHORIZO Datahub Insider	A platform built around three key data and resource streams, generated by the project CS partners and non-case study (research) partners, designed to address the specific needs of five target user groups: the scientific community, food service providers, NGOs and food banks, educational institutions and households.	EV-ILVO
Bespoke version of capacity building programme	Adaptable online/offline capacity building programme for a range of different stakeholders and aims to equip participants with the skills and knowledge to act on food waste through social norm change.	CSCP
Social norms-focused communication package	6 communication packages developed with the relevant CS partners, including message description and background of the user and target group.	UCPH
Social norms-focused education package	Teacher guides and student activities which were designed to discuss food waste in a school setting.	UCPH
Deliverables	38 deliverables produced throughout the project (mainly reports) documenting the progress and specific project objectives.	various
Practise Abstracts	10 short summaries providing end-users key information, clear recommendations and best practices to be applied in their daily routines.	FIAB
Newsletters	12 Newsletters aimed to inform the stakeholders about all CHORIZO activities	FIAB
Policy brief	Policy recommendations based on the results (D6.8)	EV-ILVO

The outputs identified in §2.1 are mapped as follows: *Insigher* is documented in §3.2.3 (Status Report on the EU FLW Prevention Hub) and analysed in §4.3 (usage analytics, global reach); the *Rapid Appraisal/Visualizer* (D3.5) is described in §4.3 (packaging WP3 modelling for reuse); the *capacity-building programme* and *Helpdesk* appear in §3.2.4 (Hub entries) and §4.3 (feedback results); *practice abstracts* are in §3.2.5 (EIP-AGRI/EU CAP Network); *clustering with sister/peer projects* is evidenced in §4.1–§4.2 (dated records and partners); and *SLA readiness* for post-project federation is set out in §4.4 (principles and draft templates).

2.2 Overview of EU-driven initiatives related to FLW

Over the course of the project, the consortium has actively mapped and engaged with a broad range of EU key initiatives in order to foster knowledge-sharing mechanisms, alignment of approaches and promote clustering activities. This was a continuous exercise and more details are reported in the C&D deliverables (D6.2, D6.3 and D6.4).

This process has combined several types of work that support one another:

- **Engagement with EU-funded projects:** Identifying and connecting with ongoing EU-funded projects, with particular attention to its sister project.

- **Links with European policy-driven platforms and networks:** Establishing links with relevant national and international initiatives, including sectoral associations and networks. These include the EU Platform on FLW, the EU FLW Prevention Hub, Food2030, the Farm to Fork Strategy, the European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform (ECESP), the European Consumer Food Waste Forum (ECFWF) and EIP-AGRI.
- **Collaboration with sectoral and industry-led initiatives:** Besides the EU-driven initiatives, CHORIZO also engaged with structures as [Food For Life ETP](#) (an expert forum from industry, Academia and research organisations that jointly develop research strategies to address European food system challenges), [National Food Technology Platforms](#) (NFTPs, an agro-industrial network promoted by the national federations of the Food and Drink Industry) and [Food for Life-Spain](#) (a national network linked to the international platform managed by FIAB). Additionally, synergies were sought with organisations like EUFIC (European Food Information Council) and FoodDrinkEurope, which are not EU-driven, but collaborate with the EU and play an important role in the FLW domain, especially with consumers and industry stakeholders.
- **Cooperation with the EU platform on FLW:** Collaborating with the EU Platform on FLW as a central hub for exchange and alignment. This platform has been prioritised to ensure visibility and usability from policy makers and other organizations.

2.3 Overview of previous EU-funded projects related to FLW

The C&D team reviewed a number of related projects and researched how these could be connected to CHORIZO. In essence, the approach for pursuing impact synergies as explained in D6.2 is:

- Engaging with ongoing projects: participation in various events and collaborative activities.
- Utilizing knowledge from previous projects: understand the results and lessons learned through the CHORIZO member who participated.
- Integrating National FLW efforts: invitation of key stakeholders to join the External Advisory Board to ensure their valuable input and recommendations.

Here is a list of them (Table 2):

Table 2 EU-funded projects related to FLW

PROJECT	CALL	CURRENTLY	DESCRIPTION
ZeroW	H2020-IA	Ongoing	Impact on several FLW prevention/reduction actions across the F2F chain
SISTERS	H2020-IA	Ongoing	Impact of FLW prevention/reduction actions, with specific focus on sharing food surplus through short-chain IT platforms and on smart and reusable food containers.
REFRESH	H2020-RIA	Closed	Exploring and explaining the factors influencing 'suboptimal' consumer and business practices in order to support effective interventions to prevent/reduce FLW, including the assessment of FW innovations diffusion through ABM models.
VALUMICS	H2020-RIA	Closed	Aimed at providing insight into food system dynamics, including food consumption drivers and

PROJECT	CALL	CURRENTLY	DESCRIPTION
			behaviour and successful interventions for sustainable food consumption.
UrbanWins	H2020-RIA	Closed	Aimed at developing strategic plans for waste (including FW) prevention in an urban context.
ToNoWaste	Horizon Europe	Ongoing	Working Towards a New Zero Food Waste Mindset Based on Holistic Assessment.
COMBINE	Horizon Europe	Ongoing	Consumer-level interventions across homes, schools, workplaces in 5 EU countries with a target of 30% reduction.
Breadcrumb	Horizon Europe	Ongoing	Exploring how marketing standards contribute to waste with evidence-based approaches across 5 commodities and develops guidance.
WASTELESS	Horizon Europe	Ongoing	Developing a harmonized measurement/ monitoring framework and toolbox for FLW tracking and valorisation.
FOLOU	Horizon Europe	Ongoing	Food loss prevention at primary production and measurement gaps.
FOODPathS	Horizon Europe	Ongoing	Co-developing a prototype European Partnership for Sustainable Food Systems.
SECUREFOOD	Horizon Europe	Ongoing	Enhancing food security using a systems-thinking framework and digital toolkit to manage risks by building food system resilience.
CATALYSE	Horizon Europe	Ongoing	Bridging scientific innovation and food safety by translating research into accessible tools, education, and collaborations across the food chain.
VERNE	Horizon Europe	Ongoing	Establishing a "One-Stop-Shop" for scalable, circular solutions in sustainable tourism, validated in five EU destinations.

2.4 Overview of the Project’s Liaison activities

This section sets out the liaison channels that underpinned T5.3. Table 2 shows partner/forum, nature of liaison, timeframe (M25–M36), and cross-references to the sections where each interaction is documented. The table focuses on structured exchanges with sister/peer projects and targeted fora to maximise complementarity and avoid duplication.

Table 3 Nature of liaison per partner/forum, timeframe and corresponding deliverable section

PARTNER/FORUM	NATURE OF LIAISON	TIMEFRAME	SECTION
ToNoWaste (GA 101059849)	Exchange-level collaboration; data exchange & platform interfacing agreed in principle	2024–2025	§4.2; §4.3 (syndication notes)
COMBINE (GA 101158394)	Exchange-level collaboration; feedback session to Insider envisaged	2024–2025	§4.2; §4.3 (syndication notes)
ZeroW (GA 101036388)	Joint programming culminating in the multi-stakeholder final conference	2024–2025	§4.2; §4.3

PARTNER/FORUM	NATURE OF LIAISON	TIMEFRAME	SECTION
FAO	Exploratory presentation and liaison (showcasing/synergies)	31 July 2025	§4.2
WASTELESS/FOLOU	Two-day webinar featuring CHORIZO presentation	17–18 June 2024	§5 (synergies & events)
RETASTE 2024	Conference talk on CHORIZO city insights	25–27 Sept 2024	§5 (synergies & events)
Open Food Conference	Session participation (first CHORIZO results)	11–13 Mar 2024	§5 (synergies & events)
MODEL2BIO	Ecosystem liaison touchpoint (industry/policy audience)	19 October 2023	§5 (synergies & events)

3 OPEN ACCESS OF THE PROJECT'S RESULTS AND OUTPUTS

Open access is described in the [Annotated GA](#) as the “online access to research outputs provided free of charge to the end-user”. The CHORIZO consortium is aware of the importance of open access (OA) and its promotion from all Horizon projects as a principle. It is critical to meet the EU requirements for responsible research and build trust in the research outcomes and recommendations.

More specifically, the main requirements and principles which are most relevant are:

- All beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results via a trusted repository.
- Beneficiaries should retain sufficient rights to enable open access, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights.

According to the [Council of the EU](#) (2016), open science is essential to “increase the quality, impact and benefits of science” and accelerate progress toward societal challenges.

For CHORIZO, this means that the results of the project can support broader EU FLW goals by being reused and adapted. The project is aligned with the EU’s Open Science policy and uses the open access as a means to maximise the value and the outreach.

3.1 Rationale and approach to alignment with EU-driven initiatives

According to the latest [scoping report of the Open Research Europe](#), EU’s dedicated platform for open access publishing, the European Commission has systematically established open access as its primary publishing model.

Their commitment is reinforced by:

- The revised 2018 Recommendation on ‘[Access to and preservation of scientific information](#)’. It recommends immediate open access to all publicly funded publications.
- The launch of a dedicated free platform for open-access publishing - Open Research Europe
- The [ERA Policy Agenda \(2022-2024\)](#), the [Council Conclusions \(2022\)](#) and the [Council Conclusions 2023](#) which encourage non-profit, open access publishing platforms and business models as well as investment in open infrastructure.

In parallel, CHORIZO results also align with the broader EU-driven initiatives (Figure 2):

- European Green Deal: aims for climate neutrality by 2050 and includes measures to eliminate unnecessary packaging, promoting reuse systems and increasing recycling rates.
- Farm to Fork Strategy: the core of the EU’s food policy, aims to reshape food systems with FW prevention as a central action.
- Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): especially target 12.3 where EU Member states have committed to cut retail and consumer food by 50% by 2030.

- EU Circular Economy Action Plan: focuses on the importance of continuous use and reuse of products, resources and materials.

Figure 2 EU Initiatives to reduce/prevent food waste and shape the relevant market

On top of that, CHORIZO’s commitment to being open and transparent is in line with the [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science framework](#), which promotes knowledge as a global public good.

In this deliverable, “connection to EU-driven initiatives” is evidenced as alignment and interfacing with established Commission-endorsed channels for open access and reuse. Practically, CHORIZO (i) **surfaced** its outputs on the EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub (resources, status reporting, capacity items); (ii) **complemented** dissemination through EU practitioner channels (practice abstracts via the EIP-AGRI/EU CAP Network); and (iii) **aligned** its intervention mapping with the JRC/DG SANTE European Consumer Food Waste Forum knowledge base to avoid duplication. These interfaces operationalise compliance with EU open access principles while making the project’s tools and evidence findable and reusable by policy, industry and practitioner audiences. Cross-references and links are provided in §3.2.

3.2 Interface of project results with EU accessible resources

EU accessible resources are publicly available information, tools, platforms and data which have received funding or endorsement by the European Commission.

3.2.1 Ensuring complementarity between CHORIZO’s database of actions and the European Consumer Food Waste Forum (ECFWF)

The European Consumer Food Waste Forum (ECFWF) is set up by DG SANTE and the JRC and its work is similar to the overall aim of CHORIZO in terms of looking at “levers for behavioural change” towards FLW. However, the forum’s focus is mainly on the consumer, whereas CHORIZO has a broader scope. The forum was active from 2021 to 2024 and several of the partners in CHORIZO are experts for the ECFWF.

The list of interventions (actions) identified by the forum has been shared with CHORIZO, to avoid duplication of work and foster complementarity. WP1 assessment of the actions identified in the CHORIZO project, has built upon the work of the ECFWF. The interventions identified in CHORIZO cover all stages of the food supply chain, and examine the economic, social, and environmental impacts of the interventions (keeping in line with the EC environmental footprint method, and in particular looking into GHG emissions, as well as land and water use).

3.2.2 Connecting CHORIZO’s Database of actions with the EU FLW Prevention Hub

As part of the work within WP1 on identifying interventions addressing food loss and food waste in the EU, and in an effort to provide comparative insight into the applicability of particular interventions addressing specific cases of food waste generation along the supply chain, two

composite indices were created which categorize the data in accordance with the food waste hierarchy pyramid, social norms, as well as the more quantitative dimensions such as economic impacts, investment costs, and cost-benefit analysis. The aim is that the methodology used in the indices should help stakeholders determine how applicable a type of food waste reduction intervention might be for themselves and their work – i.e. perhaps the intervention can be built upon, is a model to follow, or provides “lessons learned” in the sector when it comes to reducing food waste and addressing the drivers of food waste-related behaviour.

In April 2025, a synthesis document focusing on the methodology used for the indices was accepted and uploaded onto the [FLW Hub \(ID 7771\) \(under "Resources"\)](#) and included also in the Hub's May 2025 newsletter.

3.2.3 Connecting CHORIZO's Datahub and Insider Status report with the EU FLW Prevention Hub

As part of the T2.2 'CHORIZO FLW Insider datahub development & validation' and relevant deliverable D2.2 'CHORIZO FLW Insider', the project partner EV-ILVO is responsible for providing all data collected through an API open access to the EU FLW Prevention Hub.

After several discussions (email exchanges with DG SANTE) and the conclusion that an integrated API was not technically feasible, a Status Report was created and published in the EU FLW Prevention Hub. The report includes an overview of the inventory of 585 resources from the CHORIZO project and links to the corresponding API documentation site. The Status Report on the EU FLW Prevention Hub will be updated with a final version at the end of the project. This will ensure that the most recent version of all resources on the datahub and the updated API documentation is made available.

3.2.4 Connecting CHORIZO capacity building programmes with the EU FLW Prevention Hub

As part of the T4.4 'Design & delivery of activities to enhance actors' capacity to deliver change and innovate' and relevant deliverable D4.4 'Capacity building and Help desk', the project partner CSCP is responsible for designing and offering bespoke capacity building programmes.

Overall different programmes were designed for school food actors, food service actors, city actors, food banks and general public. The events were published in the [EU FLW Prevention Hub](#) and an article about the programme was featured in the [EU FLW Prevention Hub Newsletter](#).

3.2.5 Connecting CHORIZO's Practice Abstracts with the European Innovation Partnership Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI) website

A “practice abstract” is a short summary which describes a main information/recommendation/practice that can be used by the end-users in their daily practice. Projects can share their intermediate and final results through practice abstracts. A total target number of 10 practice abstracts is foreseen for the project. These will include practice abstracts based on CHORIZO results or activities with a particular focus on the inputs from the remaining Case Studies and the tools developed within the project to enhance the impact of the results, namely, the Datahub, the FLW Rapid Appraisal Tool, and the sector-specific capacity building programme. The partner FIAB was responsible for guiding the project partners in the preparation of these short summaries that explain the different project outputs in a simple and accessible manner. FIAB coordinated both the drafting process and the publication of these abstracts on the EIP-AGRI platform, which serves as a key repository of information on numerous European projects. These summaries are focused on the CHORIZO results and activities with a particular focus on the 6 case studies and the social norms

identified. More information can be found in the relevant deliverables D6.5 'Practice abstracts - batch 1' and [D6.6 'Practice abstracts - batch 2'](#).

3.2.6 Connecting the Multi-stakeholder Conference of CHORIZO and ZeroW projects with the EU FLW Prevention Hub

As part of the T6.2 'Liaison, communication, dissemination activities' and related to the celebration of the Final Joint Conference of CHORIZO project with ZeroW project, the project partner FIAB is responsible for the dissemination of the Multi-stakeholder Conference. This event took place in Brussels on September 16, 2025, bringing together innovators, policymakers, and experts, to discover innovative tools, and join discussions on critical topics such as packaging innovations, policy strategies, and how we can move closer to a zero-food-waste future. For clustering and federation routes, see Section 4.

3.2.7 Joint Research Centre (JRC): alignment beyond the ECFWF

In §3.2.1 we documented complementarity with the European Consumer Food Waste Forum (ECFWF), a DG SANTE/JRC initiative that informed CHORIZO's intervention mapping and helped avoid duplication. Beyond that forum, no additional CHORIZO-authored results were published on JRC-hosted platforms during the reporting period. The liaison value with JRC therefore comes through the ECFWF knowledge base and exchanges, while CHORIZO's public outputs are channelled via the EU FLW Prevention Hub (§§3.2.2–3.2.6) and CHORIZO's own open resources.

3.2.8 European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and open-access availability

CHORIZO's public outputs are made openly accessible in line with Horizon Europe requirements. Where appropriate, public deliverables and methods are made available from the project website; for instance, [D1.3 FLW prevention/reduction index](#).

Post-project EOSC/Zenodo depositions will be added to the website resources and cross-linked from the EU FLW Prevention Hub.

4 CLUSTERING WITH RELEVANT AND ACTIVE EU FLW PROJECTS

This chapter documents how CHORIZO operationalised T5.3's second objective: "a clustering effort with relevant and active EU FLW projects with a view to joint federation and syndication of service-oriented assets" and links those actions to the first objective of interfacing project outputs with EC-driven initiatives for open access and broader reach. In line with the Grant Agreement amendment, the clustering was designed to (i) connect CHORIZO results to EC platforms (notably the EU FLW Prevention Hub, and activities involving JRC/EC services), and (ii) cultivate collaborations with sister and peer FLW projects towards future service federation under well-established agreement principles. This deliverable also supports tracking of MS8 – Innovation impact synergies, as introduced in the Grant Agreement amendment.

Concretely, CHORIZO (a) engaged bilaterally with ToNoWaste and COMBINE through structured exchange meetings focused on methods, data, and tooling, (b) co-programmed with ZeroW around a joint final conference, and (c) surfaced core assets (the Insider/DatHub and the Rapid Appraisal Tool) via the EU FLW Prevention Hub to widen discovery and uptake. These activities were encouraged and framed by EC/JRC guidance at the CHORIZO–ToNoWaste get-together with REA, DG SANTE, JRC and RTD (25 January 2023).

4.1 Overview of the Clustering Effort

From M25 to M36, clustering proceeded on two tracks. The first track strengthened EC-facing interfaces and visibility: CHORIZO published resources to the EU FLW Prevention Hub, including the *Insighter Status Report* and topical practice abstracts, so that tools and knowledge products could be found and reused by EU interest groups (multiple resource entries are recorded in the internal draft, including IDs 7218, 7771, 7787 and a dedicated practice-abstracts item). CHORIZO also prepared dissemination for the co-hosted CHORIZO–ZeroW multi-stakeholder final event scheduled in Brussels on 16 September 2025, which the C&D plan explicitly connected to the EU FLW Prevention Hub.

The second track focused on peer-project exchanges oriented to future federation. Two structured exchange series were held with ToNoWaste (Dec 2022; Jan 2023; later follow-ups), covering comparative approaches, data/tool alignment, and potential platform interfacing (the January 2023 meeting included REA/DG SANTE/JRC/RTD and scoped next steps). Complementary exchanges with COMBINE in November 2024 and February 2025 identified pathway contributions (CHORIZO WP1/WP2/WP4 outputs as inputs to COMBINE) and envisaged feedback to the Insider/DatHub. With ZeroW, the clustering culminated in joint final-event programming to present complementary results and deliver common messages to policy officers and stakeholders. Across all three peers, collaboration remained at the exchange/information-sharing level during the reporting period (no MoUs/SLAs executed), while foundational materials (e.g., draft SLA principles) were prepared to support post-project federation.

Clustering activities in M25–M36 built directly on WP6 liaison channels and targets, which provided the contact pipeline and dissemination venues enabling the exchanges reported here and the Hub postings referenced in §4.3.

4.2 Relevant and Active EU FLW Projects

CHORIZO's clustering prioritised three EU-funded projects with strong thematic overlap and complementary assets. These are summarised below and further substantiated by the project-to-project records and CORDIS/official pages.

Table 4 Relevance & clustering with sister/peer projects

PROJECT (GA)	PROGRAMMA	RELEVANCE & CLUSTERING
ToNoWaste (GA 101059849)	Horizon Europe	Sister project under the same call; exchanges compared sustainability assessment (ToNoWaste) with social-norms-centred evidence and tools (CHORIZO), and explored datahub/platform alignment and timelines with EC/JRC participation .
COMBINE (GA 101158394)	Single Market Programme (SMP)/EC	Exchanges in Nov 2024 & Feb 2025 scoped how CHORIZO outputs (WP1/WP2/WP4) can inform COMBINE , with a planned feedback session to the Insider/Datahub; project aims at coordinated, multi-setting consumer-level interventions; a guided feedback session to Insider was requested (planned before June 2025).
ZeroW (GA 101036388)	Horizon 2020	Co-programmed a joint final conference (Brussels, 16 Sept 2025) to maximise visibility, reduce duplication, and coordinate messages to policy audiences; the event serves as a clustering focal point.

Ecosystem liaison (FAO). On 31 July 2025, CHORIZO presented its toolset to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) in an exploratory session. FAO expressed interest in learning more and in exploring potential synergies for engagement and showcasing on FAO channels; materials were exchanged and a brief follow-up call was considered useful. This outreach sits alongside EU-funded clustering and extends the project’s visibility to international platforms. (Per consortium correspondence; included here to reflect the broader ecosystem engagement alongside EU projects)¹.

Table 5 Task objectives and evidence

T5.3 OBJECTIVE	EVIDENCE
Link results to EC-driven initiatives	EU FLW Prevention Hub entries: 7218 (Insigher Status Report), 7771 (indices methodology), 7746/7787 (capacity-building items).
Cluster with relevant/active EU FLW projects	ToNoWaste minutes & agenda (14 Dec 2022; 25 Jan 2023); COMBINE exchange & follow-up notes (Nov 2024, Feb 2025); ZeroW joint final event programming (16 Sep 2025).
Prepare federation/syndication basis	Draft service-agreement principles (Scope; R&R; Access/Use; Quality; Sustainability; Feedback; Uptime/support/fees).

4.3 Joint Federation and Syndication of Service-oriented Assets

CHORIZO positioned three primary assets for future federation and syndication:

- **CHORIZO FLW “Insigher” (Datahub):** a BI-oriented evidence layer aggregating actions/tools and their performance, with a governance model for data sharing, and with entries and updates

¹ Additional relevant projects and initiatives (e.g., WASTELESS, FOLOU, BREADCRUMB, FOODPathS, SECUREFOOD, CATALYSE, VERNE) were engaged for joint webinars, café talks, conference sessions, and liaison activity; details are catalogued in the internal draft and Chapter 5.

disseminated via the EU FLW Prevention Hub. The internal draft records published items (*Insighter Status Report*; practice abstracts) and notes the planned upload of ToNoWaste data in September 2025 to facilitate cross-project discoverability. Externally, the Hub’s stakeholder newsletter reported 585 resources available in the repository, underscoring why the Hub is the right syndication venue for [CHORIZO outputs](#). The *Insighter “About” page* describes the architecture and purpose to support decision-makers. EC-facing entries on the EU FLW Prevention Hub include: *Insighter Status Report* (ID 7218), *Composite indices methodology* (ID 7771, featured in the May 2025 newsletter), and capacity-building items (IDs 7746, 7787), together positioning *Insighter* as the outward-facing catalogue for syndication; see §3 for details.

Usage (Oct 2023–Sep 2025): The *Insighter* datahub recorded² **5,024 total visits**, with the unique-visitor view counting **4,073 visits**. Traffic generated 17,792 pageviews and 11,762 unique pageviews (+2,667%), while the unique-visitor view logged 6,691 pageviews and 5,887 unique pageviews (+6,272.4%). Users carried out 543 on-site searches spanning 259 unique keywords (+18,000%), and fetched resources 402 times with 315 unique downloads (+4,366.7%); in the unique-visitor view this corresponds to 131 downloads and 90 unique downloads (+4,266.7%). Outbound engagement was strong, with 205 outbound links (52 unique; +4,000%) overall and 136 outbound links (21 unique; +13,500%) in the unique-visitor view. Depth of interaction peaked at 448 actions during a single visit (+303.6%), and 201 actions in the unique-visitor view (+704%). Taken together, these figures demonstrate rapid growth in reach and active uptake, reinforcing *Insighter*’s suitability as the vehicle to syndicate CHORIZO’s results and a credible foundation for post-project federation.

Figure 3 *Insighter*’s geographic reach: Left-Total Visits; Right-Unique Visits (screenshots from Matomo Analytics, accessed September 15, 2025)

Geographic reach: The visitor maps show a genuinely global footprint for *Insighter*, with sustained traffic across Europe and North America and additional engagement visible from Latin America, Africa, the Middle East, and the Asia–Pacific region. The unique-visitor distribution (4,073 visits) closely mirrors the total-visits view (5,024), indicating broad reach across regions rather than activity concentrated among a few repeat users. This worldwide spread underscores *Insighter*’s relevance beyond the consortium and strengthens its positioning as a credible vehicle for post-project federation and cross-project syndication.

See §3.2.3 for the *Hub Status Report* context.

² Data on *Insighter* come from *Matomo Analytics Dashboard (2025)*, accessed on September 15, 2025

- FLW Rapid Appraisal/Visualizer Tool (D3.5):** Led by UNIBO under WP3, the Rapid Appraisal/Visualizer translates behavioural modelling into an interactive interface that surfaces the main outcomes of T3.2–T3.3 for quick, scenario-based exploration. At proposal/GA-amendment level, D3.5 is a public deliverable providing “a visualizer tool that will allow users to easily access the main outcomes of the models developed in T3.2 and T3.3,” with TRL rising 2→5 by project end. The tool rests on the HUMAT–MOA behavioural architecture and a household “Pantry Manager” microsimulation that captures stock-keeping, shopping frequency, risk aversion and perishability dynamics; users can vary levers such as shopping frequency, risk-aversion (δ) and date-marking/spoilage rules, or test technology improvements that extend perishable shelf life, to see combined effects on waste-relevant behaviours and outcomes. Packaging assumptions/results in a web-based interface enables peers to inspect, replicate and reuse scenarios without code-level integration—aligning with the “federate-then-syndicate” pathway and creating a ready interface for post-project collaboration around shared scenario libraries
- Education asset for syndication: the CHORIZO board game (T4.3):** To translate social-norms insights into classroom practice and seed long-term behaviour change, CHORIZO developed a board game under T4.3. The game followed a structured pathway, from concept design, to development, to validation, in collaboration with ICLEI, UCPH and ILVO. Validation readiness was confirmed; German and French versions were completed and sets distributed to Vienna, Bremen and Dunkerque, Zaragoza proceeded with materials and feedback, and two Danish schools tested a Danish version. Feedback was positive, with targeted refinements identified—shorter sessions for younger pupils (≈ 35 –40 minutes for older pupils), gameplay structure adjustments, and layout/visual enhancements. The team agreed to prepare a spiced-up mock-up for the final event and to offer both a DIY printable and a higher-quality boxed version for dissemination. A short teacher–student survey (for product refinement, not impact assessment) supports these final edits. Collectively, the board game complements the Insider and the Rapid Appraisal/Visualizer as a syndication-ready communication product for cities and schools and a practical entry point for post-project collaboration with education networks.

Capacity-building: CHORIZO delivered sector-specific and all-sector programmes supported by a structured feedback instrument (7-point Likert scale). 27 respondents provided feedback; all rated overall session quality ≥ 5 (median 6). Tool-level signals were strong: Insider/Datahub avg 6; median 6, Visualizer avg 6; median 6.5, Miro avg 5.9; median 6, with positive intent for the LinkedIn group and Helpdesk (avg 5.6 each). Respondents covered cities, schools, food banks, HoReCa, households/consumers, packaging/processing, retail/wholesale, research. Within the schools track, the board game was showcased and taken forward with partners for validation, supporting the case for post-project federation/syndication.

Syndication during the project lifetime: Syndication prioritised visibility and alignment through the EU FLW Prevention Hub and coordinated communications rather than deep technical integration—consistent with meeting conclusions and the end-phase timeline. Concretely, CHORIZO published an Insider Status Report on the Hub (overviewing 585 resources and linking to API documentation), a methodology synthesis for the composite indices (featured in the May 2025 Hub newsletter), and capacity-building items to widen discovery (Hub IDs 7218, 7771, 7787, 7746). With ToNoWaste, data exchange and platform interfacing were agreed in principle for post-project follow-up but not enforced in the reporting period; with COMBINE, collaboration and feedback to the Insider were likewise agreed but not enforced (including a planned feedback session). Programming for the CHORIZO–ZeroW final conference (16 Sep 2025) was explicitly tied to Hub-based dissemination. These steps, together with strong Insider usage and capacity signals, validate the “federate-then-syndicate” pathway and provide a solid base for post-project federation.

Variance note: In line with meeting conclusions and end-phase timing, clustering remained at the exchange level by M36: with ToNoWaste, data exchange and platform interfacing were agreed in principle for post-project follow-up; with COMBINE, collaboration and feedback to the Insider were agreed but not enforced within the period. No MoUs/SLAs were executed; instead, Hub postings and joint programming (including the CHORIZO–ZeroW final conference, 16 September 2025) operationalised the project’s ‘federate-then-syndicate’ pathway.

4.4 Service Agreement Principles

Collaboration with peer projects remained at the exchange level as concluded before. Accordingly, this section formalises a readiness framework for post-project federation of the Insider and the Rapid Appraisal/Visualizer rather than reporting signed agreements. The internal draft sets out a compact principle set: Scope; Roles & Responsibilities; Access & Use Rights; Quality Assurance; Sustainability; Feedback Loop; Uptime, Support, Fees, as the minimal backbone for inter-project service federation and syndication, consistent with the project’s governance for the datahub and its open-science posture in the amended GA (FAIR/open access, and IPR/NDAs where applicable). To operationalise this readiness framework, CHORIZO prepared draft SLA templates for the Insider and the Rapid Appraisal/Visualizer. These are presented as illustrative examples (see Annex 8.2) and are not signed agreements.

Practically, the framework anticipates: (i) clear scope and service definitions (what the Insider and Visualizer provide, boundaries and exclusions) and named roles & responsibilities for provision/consumption; (ii) access & use rights clarity for outputs (e.g., CC-compatible terms for non-sensitive artefacts; project-specific terms where personal/sensitive data or background IP are involved); (iii) quality assurance via minimum data-quality and metadata baselines aligned with EC platform expectations (to support Hub-level discoverability); (iv) sustainability provisions for hosting/maintenance and transparent change management beyond project end; (v) uptime & support via documented service contacts, incident/issue tracking and periodic reporting against agreed targets; (vi) a formal feedback loop (e.g., scheduled reviews, change-request process and partner consultation points); and (vii) transparent fees (if any), covering cost-recovery/hosting and any optional service tiers.

Draft SLA templates available (Annex). Three templates have been prepared to support post-project federation: (i) a light SLA for project-to-project collaboration (minimal commitments around visibility and feedback); (ii) a heavier SLA for strategic partners/service providers (uptime, support, data-quality and sustainability provisions); and (iii) an SLA for the Rapid Appraisal/Visualizer (access, transparency of assumptions, feedback and acknowledgement). These models are intended to lower entry barriers for clustered projects while offering a path to more formalised service federation where appropriate. They are examples, not binding commitments, and align with the project’s “federate-then-syndicate” pathway.

5 ENCOURAGING INTEREST, ADOPTION AND BROAD SUSTAINABILITY OF PROJECT’S OUTPUTS

5.1 Target Groups

The target groups have been identified in the GA and as part of WP6 for communication purposes. In Figure 4, all actors in the food value chain relevant to CHORIZO are included. This of course includes local, regional and EU level. Details of clustering partners and activities are provided in §4.1–4.2; this section focuses on audiences, channels and event outcomes.

Figure 4 Target groups

5.2 Synergies with Sister Project – ToNoWaste

This project was funded from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation actions under grant agreement No 101059849 (topic: HORIZON-CL6-2021-FARM2FORK-01-13 - Evidence-based decision-making to change social norms towards zero food waste).

Replying to the same call, both projects share the goal of increasing sustainability to the food systems by using multi-stakeholder engagement and evidence-based approaches. This common objective to influence decision-making and reduce FLW across the food chain offered a clear synergy for collaboration. Several meetings were held between the sister projects with the following exchanges included below:

- Overview of the two projects which led to the recognition of common and different points in the approach, tools, methodologies and goals (14/12/22).

Concerning the open innovations ecosystem: both projects working with previous project information and agreed to share their deliverables and keep each other informed.

The two projects have identified that they are looking at the same sources but not the same datasets, as the type of information that we are trying to get is different and complementary. CHORIZO will focus on the understanding of SN behind a decision and why it took place and has a limited timeframe for the analysis. TNW will focus on how the actions are assessed and how

sustainable a solution is. Therefore, the CHORIZO analysis will be considered from TNW for which parameters consumers consider in their behaviour.

First discussion on possible alignment between CHORIZO Datahub and the data platform of TNW. EV-ILVO presented the idea of the CHORIZO Datahub but there are some obstacles in collaborating due to agenda nonconformity (first prototype of the platform will be ready on M31 and CHORIZO projects ends 5months later).

First draft of final indicators will be shared (Jul23) from TNW to CHORIZO.

- Both projects were presented in a Get Together meeting with the REA, SANTE, JRC and RTD representatives (25/01/23). The goal of the meeting was to achieve a clearer view on the next steps and align on areas for collaboration between the projects and the JRC/EC services.
- Knowledge exchange session (21/11/24) with the presentation on TNW sustainability assessment framework and presentation on CHORIZO FLW inventory and evidence-based analysis of FLW actions.

TNW will use the key success factors for each sector described in CHORIZO's deliverables D1.2 and D1.4.

Contribution of CHORIZO training packages in the respective TNW deliverable (due Aug.25).

- Knowledge exchange session (27/11/24) with TNW presentation on the measurement method TNW uses to collect consumer data and CHORIZO's presentation on the modelling work. This session focused on exchanges on the recruitment of the participants on the interventions and difficulties faced by both projects.
- Participation of CHORIZO in technical workshop "Challenges to Evaluate the Sustainability of Food Waste Prevention & Reduction Solutions" in January 2025 from partners FIAB, CSCP and ICLEI. The session showcased the ToNoWaste framework and the potential of ICT innovations to aid informed decision-making in this critical area. CHORIZO's goal was to increase awareness about the project.

This workshop provided a platform to gain a deeper understanding of sustainability evaluation methods, explore ICT tools tailored for FW prevention and reduction and network with experts and stakeholders committed to creating a sustainable food system.

- Participation of CHORIZO in the technical workshop "Technical Workshop: "Innovating for a Sustainable Future: Addressing Food Loss and Waste Science Challenges" in May 2025 in person (INLEIN) and online (VLTN). VLTN presented key challenges explored in the CHORIZO project related to social norms and both partners participated in a brainstorming session aimed at identifying research gaps and proposing actionable solutions to guide future efforts in the field. INLEIN also participated in the social action organised by the Municipality of Halandri.
- Input from CHORIZO to the mapping survey performed from TNW project in June 2025. This included technologies that tackle food loss and waste across the entire food supply chain - from farm to fork. Partners EV-ILVO and UNIBO actively contributed with the descriptions of the CHORIZO Datahub and CHORIZO Rapid appraisal tool respectively. They provided information among others on the properties, intended users, costs, functional aspects, observed and potential impacts of the technologies.

As this has been indicated from our Project Officer, the collaboration between CHORIZO and ToNoWaste is very important, as the two projects approach very differently the same call subject and are thus complementary in many ways. This was also recognised by both consortia from the beginning and has assisted them to ensure their methodological complementarity, along with mutual learning and a goal to increase impact synergies. CHORIZO has a more qualitative approach, focusing on the role of social norms and behavioural drivers in FLW. ToNoWaste has a more quantitative approach, focusing on the assessment and sustainability of interventions and solutions.

CHORIZO's inventory on FLW actions and behavioural insights have informed TNW's assessment framework, making sure that this dimension is also included in evaluation methodologies used by the project. On the same time, the sharing of the indicators and measurement methods of TNW enriched CHORIZO's analysis. The joint workshops facilitated cross project exchange of practical insights, evidence, challenges, data collection approaches, recruitment strategies and validation on the applicability and relevance of each project's outputs.

The impact of this collaboration has been significant and provided an added value to both projects. The combination of the sustainability assessment and the behavioural evidence have concluded to an enrichment and more practical relevance of the technology inventory, creating a basis for long-term use of the outcomes.

See §4.1–4.2 for dated clustering records.

5.3 Synergies with Project – Combine

This project was funded from the European Union's Single Market Programme Food Chain under grant agreement N° 101158394 with a two-year duration. Their main goal is first to identify and then implement the most effective intervention(s) and/or a combination of them to best target three specific consumer groups. These include households, corporate restaurants and school canteens.

A few meetings were held with this project:

- Overview presentation of the COMBINE project (21/11/24) from the project coordinator, including objectives, scope and approach.
- CHORIZO's coordinator EV-ILVO shared relevant deliverables (11/02/25), specifically D2.3 "Empirical evidence sensemaking", D1.2 "Evidence-based analysis of FLW actions/tools", D1.4 "Sector-specific guidance" and D4.1 "Actor specific guidance". All of which were deemed useful for the insights and conclusions on the interventions gathered by CHORIZO.
- In depth presentation of the CHORIZO Datahub from EV-ILVO team, explaining its role as a centralized data repository and analytics tool for the project. Partner INLEIN presented some elements of the upscaling strategy and how it is envisioned to be used as a decision support tool using different services.
- Exploration and detailed feedback provided by the COMBINE team on the CHORIZO Datahub (May 2025).

Both projects immediately identified the alignment, specifically on the use of the CHORIZO Datahub, as it consolidates evidence of FLW actions and behavioural drivers and also contains specific data and empirical knowledge on the case studies about households and schools. On the same time, COMBINE's perspective and structured feedback has supported improvements to the CHORIZO Datahub and provided an external user need assessment. This synergy had a clear impact for both

directions and reinforce both projects; objectives by combining CHORIZO's insights and COMBINE's practical testing.

See §4.1–4.2 for dated clustering records.

5.4 Synergies with Project – ZeroW

This project was funded under the Green Deal call of the Horizon Programme 2020 (Grant Agreement no. 101036388). ZeroW develops and demonstrates Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) across the food supply chain, with the goal to deliver replicable solutions for Europe's food system.

The two projects decided to host a joint Final Multi-Stakeholder Conference in Brussels (16 September 2025) instead of hosting separate ones and join forces for their final dissemination activity.

Several meetings were held for the preparation, co-design and actual implementation of the Final event:

- A kick off meeting was held (25/09/24) to agree on the organisation and start mapping overlaps between the CHORIZO CSs and ZeroW SILLs.
- A total of 10 follow-up sessions between November 2024 and September 2025 were held between the two projects organising committee. In each meeting, the roadmap was updated with new information, logistics and organisational aspects were discussed, agenda items were adjusted and actions and next steps were identified. Some additional actions include:
 - 5/11/24 Presentation of the CHORIZO Case Studies and ZeroW SILLs, session recorded the session for all consortium partners.
 - 15/01/25 Presentation of the CHORIZO Datahub by EV-ILVO, first discussion on communication strategy and event visibility.
 - 10/03/25 Integration of demos, videos and policy sessions agreement.
 - 07/04/25 Merge of the templates for the breakout sessions, exploration of networking "speed dates".

The iterative meeting process used, allowed the projects to progress harmoniously and strengthen their synergy. More specifically, there is a clear complementarity between the social and behavioural insights of CHORIZO and the technological innovations of ZeroW. The first is a Research and Innovation Action project, whereas ZeroW is an Implementation Action project. This was demonstrated during the final event as each session included combined contributions from both projects, with many important subjects as communicating change, from data to actions and decision making, household behaviours, systemic barriers among others. Both projects reduced the duplication of effort, maximised their visibility with broader stakeholder participation and managed to deliver common messages to policy officers and stakeholders.

The successful final event has demonstrated that there are various ways to create more value together than separately. ZeroW and CHORIZO managed to create a coordinated approach, by combining their resources and expertise, which can serve as a model for future EU projects.

See §4.1–4.2 for dated clustering records.

5.5 Synergies with EU initiatives

Project representatives have participated in multiple EU initiatives. Notably:

- Presentation of the CHORIZO Project at the National Food Technology Platforms “Food for Life” meetings in Paris (October 2022), Valladolid (April 2023) and Prague (April 2025).
- Presentation highlighting social norms and their influence on food waste at **ALIBETOPÍAS** (FIAB RDI annual congress, October 2023) with CNTA.
- Participation in the **FOODPathS Festival 2025** (20–22 May, Brussels), including a CHORIZO session on applying social norms to reduce food waste as an interactive capacity-building slot.
- Participation in **CATALYSE** World Food Safety Day event (5 June 2025, Porto).
- **SECUREFOOD** exchange meeting to explore synergies (9 April 2025).

Additional fora:

- **MODEL2BIO** conference (19 October 2023): CHORIZO-branded intervention delivered by a project representative.
- **Open Food Conference** (11–13 March 2024): first CHORIZO results presented in a food-waste session by a project representative.
- **RETASTE 2024** (25–27 September 2024): talk “How to coordinate urban food waste reduction strategies – case insights from the EU-CHORIZO City Interest Group.”
- **WASTELESS × FOLOU** two-day webinar (17–18 June 2024): CHORIZO presentation on FLW interventions.

The objectives of these interactions are to engage with key industry stakeholders and leaders, contribute to the European partnership for Sustainable Food Systems and showcase CHORIZO’s initiatives. Therefore, the impact for CHORIZO is increasing the visibility and enhancing networking opportunities, while introducing innovative practises. As an outcome this synergy supported increased collaborative research opportunities and reinforced CHORIZO’s commitment to participatory research and approaches.

Regarding **FOOD2030** the below initiatives have taken place:

- Common Workshop with CLEVERFOOD for the FOOD 2030 Project Collaboration Network in September 2023 with partners EV-ILVO and FIAB
- FOOD 2030 conference in December 2023 with partners FIAB and EV-ILVO
- Presentation of CHORIZO in FOOD2030 Networks Conference 2024 Transformative Food System Innovation in March 2024 from EV-ILVO and UCPH

The objectives of these interactions are to exchange knowledge on key topics, identify synergies and collaboration opportunities and strengthen the European research networks, while showcasing CHORIZO’s contributions and enhancing awareness. The impact for CHORIZO is increasing the visibility of the project, gain further knowledge on capacity for citizens and public engagement and ensuring alignment with broader sectoral and policy goals. As an outcome this synergy supported increased engagement in the FOOD2030 Network and sharing of best practices and innovations.

In the **Technological Platform Food 4 life-Spain (PTF4LS)**,

- Partners CNTA and FIAB presented CHORIZO in the [Working Group of "Consumer and New products" in September 2024](#).
- The partner FIAB presented CHORIZO CS3 results based on research with interactions between retail, restaurants and consumption in Working Group of "HoReCa sector" in April 2025.

The objectives of these interactions are to present CHORIZO results to industry stakeholders in Spain, enhance dialogue and facilitate the transfer of knowledge. Concerning the impact, firstly, sharing findings with key stakeholders creates opportunities for validation in a real market. Secondly, transferring insights at national level, increases the prospects for uptake of the methodologies and tools presented.

In October 2023, the CHORIZO project represented by partner ICLEI and FIAB, participated in a high-level event named "A multi-stakeholder perspective on food loss and food waste reduction strategies" organised by **CEMAS** and **EUFIC** organisations. ICLEI participated in the panel discussion "City Networks and their key role tackling food loss and waste". This event enabled the presentation of CHORIZO research finding and engagement with city networks. As an outcome, the event highlighted the key roles of city networks and shared best practices and CHORIZO case studies and insights.

5.6 Joint C&D activities and events

In March 2024, the CHORIZO project represented by partner FIAB, participated in [Alimentaria Barcelona 2024](#), which is a leading international trade fair. CHORIZO project was presented in the framework of a Living Lab for European projects, where different topics were covered: Sustainable Food Systems, Healthy and Sustainable diets, Food Safety innovations and Fight against Food Waste. Through targeted networking and promotion on social media, the project increased awareness among key actors and reinforced connections with the private sector for future exploitation.

In June 2024, the CHORIZO project represented by partner VLTN, participated in a two-day webinar "*Current Developments in Food Loss and Waste Reduction*", organised by the [FOLOU](#) and [WASTELESS](#) projects. The event brought together several relevant EU-funded initiatives, including [TONOWASTE](#), [ZeroW](#), [SISTERS](#), [FOODRUS](#), [CULTIVATE](#), [FOODLOOPS](#), [WASTE2FUNC](#), and [LOWINFOOD](#), with the objective of fostering scientific knowledge exchange and strengthening collaboration across the EU FLW community. CHORIZO contributed through the presentation of key findings from WP1, specifically focusing on interventions addressing FLW. The interaction enabled the dissemination of CHORIZO's methodologies and tools, facilitated valuable insights into regulatory strategies and innovative practices and reinforced technological collaboration. As an outcome, the synergy supported increased awareness, capacity building, and laid the groundwork for the broader implementation of effective FLW reduction practices in line with EU policy priorities.

In October 2024, ITC represented the CHORIZO project on the biggest agri-food fair in the Slovenian region "Sejem AGRA - Mednarodni kmetijsko-živilski sejem" with a booth and rollup, along with the projects [ZeroW](#) and [BREADCRUMB](#). For CHORIZO apart from the general presentation there was also a focus on the CS3 results on the food services. The goal was to share scientific knowledge by disseminating the CS results, best practices and promoting collaboration.

In an effort to increase collaboration and dissemination between projects, CSCP team presented the CHORIZO project aims and results on social norms to [FOODLOOPS](#) team (May 2025) and the [BREADCRUMB](#) project (September 2025). While FLW connects these projects, they have different foci. [FOODLOOPS](#) targets school food and the CHORIZO team shared insights about social norms relevant in the school food field and resources developed and collected in the CHORIZO project.

BREADCRUMB deals with marketing standards and the presentation specifically focused on the relevant social norms related to that. Project partners found it insightful to look into and discuss their topics through the lens of social norms.

In May 2025, INLEIN participated in a half a day webinar organised by WASTELESS project, named: *“Value proposition, technology adoption and implementation of FLW measurement tools”*. The objective is knowledge sharing and cross project interaction with a focus on exploitation strategies and the practical adoption of FLW measurement tools. This webinar allowed CHORIZO to gain valuable insights on strategies used by other projects to ensure sustainability of the solutions and improve understanding of technology implementation barriers.

In May 2025, CHORIZO participated in the Food 4 Future Expo 2025 “ZERO WASTE: Obligations and Opportunities in the Food Chain”, organised by the BREADCRUMB project. The session, moderated by FIAB, brought together various EU-funded projects, including ZeroW, WASTELESS and Rosetta, to discuss European approaches to reducing food loss. The partner CNTA presented CHORIZO’s work on behavioural change strategies through open and responsible innovation. The event contributed to increased visibility and awareness of the project’s data-driven interventions and consumer insights.

WASTELESS project hosts a series of Monthly Café Talks, on the third Friday of every month, to engage with all stakeholders in the food value chain on topics related to Food Loss and Waste. These meetings are aimed at encouraging the exchange of views and best practices on FLW measuring, monitoring and valorisation strategies between all food value chain actors, from primary producers to consumers, policy makers, researchers and others. UNIBO presented the Rapid Appraisal Tool on the 19th of September 2025.

5.7 Coordinated Delivery of Policy Recommendations

The delivery of policy recommendation has been formed by continuous exchanges with other related Horizon Europe projects. Specifically, with ZeroW there has been a regular dialogue and CHORIZO’s policy brief was presented in the final event together with the recommendations of ZeroW. This policy brief was based on a City Interest Group (CIG) webinar, taking into consideration various discussions and inputs gathered.

Concerning ToNoWaste, discussions have taken place but as the sister project is operating under a different timeline, they shared their early policy deliverable D6.1 “Regulatory analysis of the food supply chains under study to prevent food waste”. This analysis offered new insights into the rules for preventing food waste and was factored into the development of CHORIZO’s policy brief, which will also be shared with them once finalised.

The recommendations are not developed in isolation, they are rather aligned with insights and complementary information from the wider FLW cluster, supporting a stronger impact towards EU policy processes.

6 CONCLUSION

This deliverable demonstrates that CHORIZO has fulfilled Task 5.3’s twofold brief: (i) interfacing project outputs with EC-driven initiatives for open access and reuse; and (ii) clustering with relevant and active EU FLW projects to prepare joint federation and syndication of service-oriented assets. Across M25–M36, the consortium translated evidence and tools into openly discoverable resources, built practical collaboration channels with sister/peer projects, and put in place a lightweight governance frame to carry the work beyond project end. More specifically, it delivered:

- **EC-facing openness and discoverability:** Core outputs were surfaced on the EU FLW Prevention Hub (Insighter Status Report, composite-indices methodology, capacity-building items) and complemented by practice abstracts and website resources, ensuring findability for policy, industry and practitioner audiences.
- **Syndication-ready assets:**
 1. Insighter (Datahub) operated as the outward-facing catalogue for CHORIZO results, showing strong and global uptake (5,024 visits; 17,792 pageviews; 543 on-site searches; 402 downloads) and providing a stable anchor for post-project federation.
 2. Rapid Appraisal/Visualizer (D3.5) packaged the modelling backbone into a web interface for “what-if” exploration, enabling peers to inspect, replicate and reuse scenarios without code-level integration.
 3. Board game (T4.3) progressed from concept to classroom validation, with multilingual sets in use and a printable/boxed format identified for wider syndication.
- **Clustering and outreach:** Structured exchanges with ToNoWaste and COMBINE, joint programming with ZeroW (culminating in the Brussels final conference on 16 September 2025), and targeted liaisons (e.g., FAO; cross-project webinars/events) broadened the ecosystem footprint while avoiding duplication.
- **Capacity-building signals:** Cross-actor training returned consistently high feedback (27 responses; median quality 6/7), confirming relevance for cities, schools, food services, food banks, retail/wholesale, processing/packaging and research communities.
- **Federation governance:** A concise set of service-agreement principles (scope; roles and responsibilities; access and use rights; quality assurance; sustainability; feedback loop; uptime/support/fees) and draft SLA templates were prepared to enable “lightweight SLAs” between projects and a pathway to formal agreements with EC platforms.
- **Alignment and traceability:** Activities were routed through WP6 liaison channels and support the tracking of MS8 “Innovation impact synergies.”

Actions to be completed by project end

- Publish the final update of the Insighter Status Report on the EU FLW Prevention Hub and align linked API notes.
- Deliver the CHORIZO–ZeroW multi-stakeholder final conference (16 September 2025) and upload related materials to the Hub and project channels.
- Proceed with the planned ToNoWaste data upload to the Insighter to support cross-project discoverability.

Post-project pathway

- Initiate lightweight SLAs with clustered projects using the draft templates (scope, roles, data/metadata baselines, feedback cadence).
- Syndicate the board game (printable and boxed formats) via city/school networks; continue light, structured feedback collection to inform minor iterations.
- Maintain minimal hosting and user support for the Insider and the Visualizer and continue monitoring reach/reuse using the same analytics frame.

These items remained outside the project window due to the end-phase timing of clustering agreements, the agreed emphasis on visibility and alignment (Hub entries, joint programming) and the technical conclusion not to implement a live API integration within the reporting period.

Ownership aligns with the roles already described in the report (Insighter: EV-ILVO; Visualizer: UNIBO; board game: ICLEI/UCPH/ILVO; dissemination: project team), ensuring continuity. Taken together, CHORIZO leaves a coherent “federate-then-syndicate” pathway, i.e. the results are openly accessible and in active use; the collaboration channels and principles are in place; and the project’s assets, the Insider, the Rapid Appraisal/Visualizer, and the board game, are packaged for reuse, extension and policy-relevant uptake beyond project end.

7 REFERENCES

- CHORIZO Consortium. (2023). *D1.3 – FLW prevention & reduction index*. <https://chorizoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/D1.3-FLW-prevention-reduction-index.pdf>
- CHORIZO Project. (n.d.). *About this datahub*. <https://data.CHORIZOproject.eu/about>
- CHORIZO Consortium. (2025). *D5.3 Innovation Impact Synergies (v0.4)* [internal draft]. Evidence for EU FLW Hub entries, clustering activities, and draft SLA principles.
- CHORIZO & ToNoWaste. (2022, December 14). *Collaboration ToNoWaste & CHORIZO— Minutes/agenda [internal meeting records]*. Discussion of datahub/platform alignment and timelines.
- CHORIZO, REA, DG SANTE, JRC, RTD & ToNoWaste. (2023, January 25). *Get-together meeting— Minutes and EC slide deck [internal records]*. Clustering and JRC collaboration framing.
- CHORIZO Project (Capwell Forbang Echo, C.). (2024, May 22). *CHORIZO food loss and waste Datahub & “Insigher” Status Report v1.0* (EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub resource). https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/food_waste/eu-food-loss-waste-prevention-hub/resource/show/7218 (European Commission)
- CORDIS. (2025, June 11). *ZeroW—Systemic Innovations Towards a Zero Food Waste Supply Chain: Reporting* (GA 101036388). <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101036388/reporting>
- CORDIS. (2024). *PRECIOUS—Addressing the Environmental Impacts of Food Loss and Waste Prevention and Its Rebound Effects: Fact sheet* (GA 101181994). <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101181994>
- CORDIS. (n.d.). *Projects & results—Search portal*. <https://cordis.europa.eu/projects>
- Council of the European Union. (2016, May 27). *The transition towards an Open Science system: Council conclusions* (ST-9526/16). <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-9526-2016-INIT/en/pdf>
- Council of the European Union. (2021, November 26). *Council Recommendation (EU) 2021/2122 on a Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe* (ST-14308/21). <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-14308-2021-INIT/en/pdf>
- Council of the European Union. (2022, June 10). *Council conclusions on research assessment and implementation of Open Science* (10126/22). <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/56958/st10126-en22.pdf>
- Council of the European Union. (2023, May 23). *Council conclusions on high-quality, transparent, open and trustworthy scholarly publishing* (ST-9616/23). <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-9616-2023-INIT/en/pdf>
- European Commission, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation. (2024, September 4). *Open Research Europe: Towards a collective open access publishing service—Scoping report* (DOI 10.2777/204155). <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/204155>
- European Commission, DG SANTE. (2024, May 29). *News from the EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub—May 2024* (Newsletter). <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/sante/newsletter-archives/53499>

- European Commission. (2018, April 25). *Commission Recommendation (EU) 2018/790 on access to and preservation of scientific information*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32018H0790&from=EN>
- European Commission. (2025, April 1). *Annotated Grant Agreement (AGA), version 2.0 (2021–2027)*. https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf
- European Commission, DG SANTE. (2025). *EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub newsletter—CHORIZO Insider Status Report; 585 resources on the Hub*. Retrieved September 2025.
- European Commission. (n.d.). *ZeroW—Systemic Innovations Towards a Zero Food Waste Supply Chain* (Grant Agreement No. 101036388). CORDIS. (accessed September 2025).
- European Commission. (n.d.). *ToNoWaste—Towards a new zero food waste mindset based on holistic assessment* (Grant Agreement No. 101059849). CORDIS. (accessed September 2025).
- EU CAP Network. (n.d.). *CHORIZO (Changing practices and Habits through Open, Responsible, and social Innovation towards Zero food waste)*. https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/projects/CHORIZO-changing-practices-and-habits-through-open-responsible-and-social-innovation-0_en
- EU FLW Prevention Hub. (n.d.). *Resources page* (general). https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/food_waste/eu-food-loss-waste-prevention-hub/resource/show/7746 (European Commission)
- EV-ILVO / CHORIZO. (n.d.). *CHORIZO Datahub (Insighter): About*. Retrieved September 2025. <https://insighter-project-chorizo.ew.r.appspot.com/about>
- EUFIC. (2024). *COMBINE: Evaluating combinations of interventions to reduce consumer food waste*. EUFIC. <https://www.eufic.org/> (accessed September 2025).
- FIT4FOOD2030. (2019, June 17). *European Technology Platform (ETP) “Food for Life” (F4L)*. <https://fit4food2030.eu/partner/european-technology-platform-etp-food-life-f4l/>
- Food 2030 Projects. (2024). *COMBINE*. <https://food2030projects.eu/> (accessed September 2025).
- Food for Life-Spain (PTF4LS). (n.d.). *Plataforma Tecnológica “Food for Life”-Spain*. <https://foodforlife-spain.es/>
- Matomo. (2025). *Analytics dashboard*. Matomo Analytics. <https://matomo.org> (accessed September 2025).
- Mundo Sabor. (n.d.). *[LinkedIn post referencing CHORIZO]*. https://www.linkedin.com/posts/mundo-sabor_praercticas-haerbitos-cerodesperdicioalimentario-ugcPost-7241786387677491201-1pB3
- National Food Technology Platforms (NFTP). (n.d.). *Front-page slideshow*. <http://nftps.eu/front-page-slideshow>.
- NOVA-CICS. (2025). *COMBINE-Evaluation of combinations of interventions to reduce consumer food waste* (Reference SMP-FOOD-2023-FW-STAKEHOLDERS-AG 101158394). <https://cics.nova.fcsh.unl.pt> (accessed September 2025).

SANTE-EU FLW Prevention Hub. (2023–2025). *CHORIZO resources on the Hub* (incl. Resource 7848 and related entries). <https://food.ec.europa.eu/safety/food-waste/eu-food-loss-waste-prevention-hub> (accessed September 2025).

UNESCO. (2021). *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*.
<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949.locale=en>

WASTELESS / EU FLW Prevention Hub. (2025, May 13). *Capacity-building programme (CHORIZO)* (EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub resource). https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/food_waste/eu-food-loss-waste-prevention-hub/resource/show/7787

WASTELESS / EU FLW Prevention Hub. (2023, September 29). *Methodology for composite indices on food waste interventions (CHORIZO)* (EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub resource).
https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/food_waste/eu-food-loss-waste-prevention-hub/resource/show/7771

8 APPENDICES

8.1 List of all CHORIZO deliverables

Table 6 All CHORIZO deliverables

DELIVERABLE	DELIVERABLE NAM	W P	SHORT NAME OF LEAD
D1.1	Data protocol	1	NORCE
D1.2	Evidence-based analysis of FLW actions/tools	1	VLTN
D1.3	FLW prevention/reduction index	1	VLTN
D1.4	Sector-specific guidance	1	EV-ILVO
D2.1	Case studies' Strategic Plans	2	EV-ILVO
D2.2	CHORIZO FLW 'Insighter'	2	EV-ILVO
D2.3	Empirical evidence sensemaking	2	VLTN
D3.1	Conceptual framework for behavioural change understanding	3	UNIBO
D3.2	OFLW interventions	3	UNIBO
D3.3	Case-independent changing social norms predictive model	3	NORCE
D3.4	OFLW impact scenarios	3	UNIBO
D3.5	FLW rapid appraisal/visualizer tool	3	UNIBO
D4.1	Actor specific guidance	4	CSCP
D4.2	Social norms-focused communication products	4	UCPH
D4.3	Social norms-focused science education package	4	UCPH
D4.4	Capacity building and Help desk	4	CSCP
D5.1	Innovation Management & Exploitation	5	INLEIN
D5.2	CHORIZO Datahub Services Layer Upscaling Strategy	5	INLEIN
D5.3	Innovation Impact Synergies	5	INLEIN
D5.4	Sustainability Strategy: EU FW Associations	5	FIAB
D6.1	CHORIZO website	6	FIAB
D6.2	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan	6	FIAB
D6.3	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan – update 1	6	FIAB
D6.4	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan – update 2	6	FIAB
D6.5	Practice abstracts – batch 1	6	FIAB
D6.6	Practice abstracts – batch 2	6	FIAB
D6.7	City Interest Group's' reporting	6	ICLEI
D6.8	Policy brief	6	EV-ILVO
D7.1	Project Handbook	7	EV-ILVO
D7.2	Data Management Plan	7	EV-ILVO
D7.3	Data Management Plan – update 1	7	EV-ILVO
D7.4	Data Management Plan – update 2	7	EV-ILVO
D7.5	Quality & Risk Assessment Report	7	EV-ILVO
D7.6	Quality & Risk Assessment Report – update 1	7	EV-ILVO
D7.7	CHORIZO's impact assessment	7	INLEIN
D8.1	OEI - Requirement No. 1	8	EV-ILVO
D8.2	OEI - Requirement No. 2	8	EV-ILVO
D8.3	OEI - Requirement No. 3	8	EV-ILVO

8.2 Draft Service Level Agreements (Examples)

In order to address the expected outcome of establishing service federation agreements with active EU FLW projects, CHORIZO has developed two **complementary SLA models** for the Datahub and one SLA model for the Rapid Appraisal Tool. The rationale is that collaboration needs differ across stakeholders:

- A **light SLA** is designed for other EU FLW projects, with minimal commitments (regular updates, mutual visibility, and feedback exchange), lowering barriers to collaboration while ensuring mutual benefits.
- A **heavier SLA** sets out more operational and sustainability-oriented commitments (uptime, support, quality assurance, and possible cost-sharing), suitable for strategic partners or service providers who require a more formalised framework.
- For the **Rapid Appraisal Tool**, a dedicated SLA template outlines principles of access, feedback, and acknowledgement, enabling structured collaboration around its application and improvement.

By providing these templates as **illustrative examples** (Annex 8.2), CHORIZO ensures that a practical framework exists to support immediate project-to-project clustering, while also laying the groundwork for longer-term sustainability and exploitation pathways beyond the lifetime of the project.

8.2.1 Light SLA (CHORIZO Datahub – for EU FLW Projects)

Purpose: Enable collaboration and basic service federation among EU FLW projects, ensuring visibility, feedback, and improvement without heavy commitments.

Scope:

- Access to CHORIZO Datahub results (datasets, evidence summaries, policy insights).
- Sharing updates on integration and usage.

Partner Commitments:

- Provide **monthly feedback** on usability, integration potential, and gaps.
- Acknowledge **CHORIZO Datahub** as a source when information is used in publications, presentations, or deliverables.
- Promote the Datahub at least **once per reporting period** in dissemination events or communication materials.
- Suggest improvements and provide input on new features via a short **monthly update cycle**.

CHORIZO Commitments:

- Provide access to the Datahub (read-only, with metadata descriptions).
- Issue monthly updates (new datasets, functionalities).
- Include partner logos/names as “collaborating projects” on Datahub-related materials.

Duration:

Valid until end of CHORIZO project (Sept 2025), renewable upon mutual agreement.

8.2.2 Heavy SLA (CHORIZO Datahub – for Strategic Partners or Service Providers)

Purpose: Ensure operational-level commitments to service continuity, sustainability, and value creation beyond the project.

Scope:

- Full access to CHORIZO Datahub services (including APIs, dashboards, metadata exchange).
- Federation of selected datasets into partner platforms.

CHORIZO Commitments:

- **Uptime:** 95% monthly uptime target.
- **Maintenance:** Scheduled downtime announced at least 5 business days in advance.
- **Support:** Response to partner technical queries within 5 business days.
- **Data Quality:** Ensure all datasets are anonymised, validated, and FAIR-compliant.
- **Updates:** Quarterly release notes for improvements and bug fixes.

Partner Commitments:

- Cover agreed **hosting/operational fees** (if applicable, e.g. after project end).
- Promote the CHORIZO Datahub in **at least 2 dissemination events annually**.
- Provide structured **quarterly feedback** on usability and interoperability.
- Participate in **joint federation workshops** for alignment with EU FLW initiatives.

Duration:

Renewable SLA, with annual review of commitments.

8.2.3 SLA (FLW Rapid Appraisal Tool)

Purpose: Provide structured collaboration on the usage and improvement of the CHORIZO Rapid Appraisal Tool.

Scope:

- Access to the tool for rapid assessment of FLW prevention/reduction scenarios.
- Use in policy, business, or research contexts by external partners.

CHORIZO Commitments:

- Provide access to the tool in web-based format.
- Maintain a **basic user guide** and FAQs.
- Ensure that model outputs are transparent (assumptions documented).
- Gather and integrate feedback into iterative tool updates (every 6 months).

Partner Commitments:

- Use the tool for **testing and validation purposes** and share results of application.
- Provide **bi-annual feedback** on tool usability, clarity of results, and potential improvements.
- Acknowledge CHORIZO in publications/events where tool outputs are used.
- Optionally, provide anonymised case data for further calibration.

Duration:

Valid for the duration of CHORIZO project and extendable post-project if maintained by a hosting entity.

The logo for the CHORIZO PROJECT. The word "CHORIZO" is in a bold, sans-serif font. The letter "C" is dark grey with a small green dot and a thin grey line extending from its top-left. The letters "O", "R", "I", and "Z" are dark grey, while "H" and the final "O" are a vibrant green. Below "CHORIZO", the word "PROJECT" is written in a smaller, dark grey, sans-serif font, with the letter "O" also in green.

CHORIZO
PROJECT